

Exploring London Women's
Awareness of Technology-
Facilitated Domestic Abuse:
A Qualitative Interview-Based Study.

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8302836 | ISSN: 2977-1676

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www.journalcjd.org

British Library Registered ISSN: 2977-1676

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8302836>

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Acknowledgements

I would like to express my deep gratitude to my supervisor, Dr. Shaun S. Yates, for his valuable guidance, support, and mentorship throughout the course of this research. I would also like to thank the participants who generously shared their time and experiences for this study.

Furthermore, I would like to acknowledge the support of my family and friends, and express deep appreciation to my husband and mother, who provided me with encouragement and support throughout this journey.

Abstract

This study investigates the awareness of technology-facilitated domestic abuse among women in London through a qualitative interview-based approach. Seven women aged between 30-45 were interviewed, and their experiences and perceptions of technology-facilitated domestic abuse were analysed using thematic analysis. The results revealed two important key aspects. Firstly, communication through technology in intimate relationships can easily become a tool for domestic abuse, and the participants had frequently experienced such abuse, which can significantly impact their psychological and sociological well-being. Secondly, the study draws attention to the lack of awareness of the existing legislation and different forms of technology-facilitated domestic abuse, including the ways abusers use technology to control and manipulate their victims. The study highlights the need for greater awareness, education, and policy changes. Addressing Technology-Facilitated Domestic Abuse requires a collaborative effort from the public and private sectors, along with the community, to take responsibility in generating awareness and finding practical solutions. It is essential that all stakeholders work together to raise awareness of the serious consequences of TFDA and how the law can protect individuals. This collaborative approach is crucial to creating a safer and more equitable society for all.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Rocha-Silva (2021) observed a notable advancement in technology over the last decade, which has facilitated the widespread expansion of digital communication. Technological devices have earned significant importance in people's day by day lives, facilitating communication, especially in intimate relationships (Morey et al. 2013). Technology helps couples strengthen the relationship by maintaining proximity through an easier and instant communication (Laliker and Lannutti, 2014; also see Mosley and Lancaster, 2019; Reed et al., 2016). Despite the benefits of digital communication, scholars also discussed that technology contributed to a shift of traditional intimate abuse (Rocha-Silva, 2021). Zweig et al. (2013) argued that before the use of technological devices expanded, domestic abuse had the tendency to occur, especially when involved people were sharing the same physical space. Harris and Woodlock (2019) explained that, together with the extensive use of technological devices, intimate abuse can happen instantaneously because the individuals became available any time of the day (also argued by Melander, 2010). Technology-facilitated domestic abuse is a phenomenon that recently raised questions and extensive research has been done, but there is still a lack of academic agreement on how to define this phenomenon (Brown and Hegarty, 2018; also see Duerksen and Woodin, 2019a; Lara, 2020).

In the discourse on domestic abuse, various scholars have deliberated upon the differences between the terms 'victim' and 'survivor'. They contend that recognising both terms is significant as they reveal how women cope with an abusive relationship and the measures they adopt in such circumstances (Dunn, 2004; Gondolf and Fisher, 1988). This division of terms that have the same action roots influences people in different important social aspects (Picart, 2003). In the present research, the term 'victim' will be used and refer to women who experienced, still experience or might be at risk of experiencing any form of domestic abuse. As Lamb (1996) explained, must take into consideration that a 'victim' is not considered responsible and cannot be blamed for the abusive behaviour that is conducted towards her. In comparison with the term 'survivor', an individual labelled as a 'victim' can also be characterised by a sense of entrapment, whereby they feel unable to extricate themselves from the abusive behaviour and may not take any steps to do so (Dunn, 2004). Researchers with experience in domestic abuse have examined a novel manifestation of abuse that employs technology as a means for perpetrators to exert controlling behaviour without needing to be physically close to the victim (Yardley, 2020). Yardley (2020) coined the terminology 'technology-facilitated domestic abuse (TFDA)' to refer to a type of abuse perpetrated through the use of networked technologies and digital tools.

This form of abuse enables perpetrators to engage in controlling, harassing, monitoring, and abusive behaviours towards their current or former intimate partners (argued also by Dragiewicz et al., 2018; Brown et al., 2018). Coercive control is another term used by researchers and is described as a type of behaviour conducted with the help of technology, and also depicted by Beck (2009) as an act of dominance and control in relationship, maintained through violence, intimidation and threats (also discussed by Stark, 2006). Commonly, coercive control can be established by implementing punishment-based consequences or by using negative reinforcement (Dutton et al., 2006).

Regarding technology-facilitated domestic abuse, stalkers can effortlessly engage in this behaviour, as they do not need to be physically present to intimidate their victims. Digital communication technology provides all necessary tools for harassing and threatening behaviours that are typically associated with stalking (Hand et al., 2009). However, the lack of a comprehensive definition of the term 'stalking' poses a challenge for scholars and government agencies, making it difficult for legislation to be applied in all situations (Bocij and McFarlane, 2002). From a legislative point of view, technology-facilitated abuse has found a partial regulation in many countries and Human Rights agencies helped in solving some cases (Dunn, 2020). An example of law improvement can be seen in the past two decades in UK's legislation, which recognise online stalking as an offence in Protection of Freedom Act 2012 (Government, 2012), but the Malicious Communication Act 1998 also mentioned some aspects of stalking (Government, 2011). Coercive, controlling and harassing behaviours are mentioned in the Cybercrime - Prosecution Guidance, which accounts for the digital environment and are considered offenses (Crown Prosecution Service, 2019). But it is important to acknowledge that one of the oldest offences that was taken into consideration is 'unauthorised access with intent to commit or facilitate commission of further offence' from the Computer Misuse Act 1990 (Government, 1990).

Over the past few decades, domestic abuse has emerged as a significant area of research in the field of violence, and Dobash and Dobash (2004) argued there may be symmetry in men's and women's use of violence, although the motivation behind the violence may differ based on gender. Though, Hamberger and Larsen (2015) explained that is still a lack of clarity about the connection between control and gender. Until recently, there has been limited focus on technology-facilitated domestic abuse. Current research mostly concentrates on how technology affects young people's relationships (Brown et al., 2021) and the victimization of women (Laxton, 2013; Harris and Woodlock, 2019). As research shows, men have the tendency to be more violent than women (Tjaden and Thoennes, 2000), and physical violence has a strong relation with technology because it helps the perpetrator overcome the physicality issue in order to coerce, control and harass the victim. This has as result men being more

likely to make use of technology to facilitate domestic abuse (Harris and Woodlock, 2019; Fernet et al., 2019). Conversely, research focused on teenagers and young adults reveals that both young males and females engage in controlling behaviour through technology. They utilise various digital tools to stalk their partners and disclose intimate details about their relationships (Brown et al., 2021; Aghtaie et al., 2018). These findings raising the idea of behaviour normalisation among young people (Harris and Woodlock, 2019). Being a relatively recent issue, the government still finds it difficult to regulate online abuse (Laxton, 2013), and this confirms the need for further research to better understand the nature and prevalence of violent behaviour and victimisation facilitated by technology (Maher et al., 2017).

The aim of this study is to explore the knowledge and perception of technology-facilitated domestic abuse among 30-45 years old London women. Specifically, the present study aims to investigate the role that communication technology plays in the lives of 30-45 years old females in London, particularly in the context of intimate relationships. The study seeks to explore how technology is being used in relationships, including the ways in which it is used to communicate, control, and monitor partners. Additionally, the study aims to assess the level of knowledge that these women have about the laws surrounding technology-facilitated domestic violence. This includes understanding the implications of actions and different tools that can be used. Finally, in view of the relationship between domestic violence and digital technologies, the study seeks to identify potential policy reforms that could better protect individuals from technology-facilitated domestic abuse and suggest future research direction.

The subsequent chapters of this work will build upon the introductory discussion presented in the preceding section. Through a systematic exploration of the literature and original analysis, the paper will further investigate the central theme of this study, aiming to deepen the understanding of its complexities and nuances. In the following sections will explain the key concepts and theoretical frameworks that underpin the investigation, while also clarifying the methodological approach and data analysis techniques employed. Towards the end of the paper, the critical discussion chapter will go through a rigorous examination of the key topics, where evidence will be presented and analysed, followed by the final chapter, where conclusions will be presented.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The literature review argues that technology-facilitated domestic abuse is a new way in which intimate partners can harm each other, an extension of the traditional ways in which they engage in aggressive behaviour (Woodlock, 2017). Studies show that communication through technology affects young people's relationships as much as adults' (Brown et al., 2021). This chapter supports these arguments by first explaining the most prevalent methods and tools partners can use with the help of technology to abuse each other (Dragiewicz et al., 2019), and looking at the reports on how governmental institutions and other organisations take action to support victims, protect and regulate this type of harmful behaviours (Laxton, 2013). Second, the section will discuss how technology-facilitated abuse affects teenagers' and young adults' intimate relationships (Brown et al., 2021). The last point of the section highlights the view of victims and specialists on how technology-facilitated domestic abuse is perceived: as a normal – romantic behaviour (Woodlock, 2013), or as a harmful behaviour which should be regulated by the government (Laxton, 2013). Taken together, these points show a gap in the existing literature regarding people's awareness and comprehension of technology-facilitated domestic abuse methods and regulations.

2.2 Technology-facilitated domestic abuse

Scholars began to address the problem of intimate adult partner violence several decades ago, and government institutions have recently taken steps to regulate it. This behaviour is now commonly referred to as domestic abuse or violence, and encompasses emotional, physical, financial, and sexual forms of abusive and coercive/controlling behaviour (Home Office, 2012); Woodlock (2013) argued that domestic abuse might be also achieved through digital devices, especially for stalking, harassment and coercive control (ideas researched and discussed also by Dragiewicz et al., 2019; Duerksen and Woodin, 2019; Harris and Woodlock, 2019). To describe domestic abuse enabled through technology, scholars used terms like 'technology-facilitated stalking' (Woodlock, 2017), 'technology-facilitated coercive control' (Dragiewicz et al., 2019), 'digital coercive control' (Harris & Woodlock, 2019), or 'technological intimate partner violence' (Duerksen & Woodin, 2019). Yardley (2020) used a wider term like 'technology-facilitated domestic abuse', which refers to all the abusive methods in which technology is being used to harm intimate partners or ex-partners. In their research Southworth et al. (2007) showed what tools perpetrators used to abuse their partners/ex-partners: cellular phones, e-mails, fax machines, spyware, GPS (global positioning system), video cameras, calling cards and caller

identification, computers, keystroke logging hardware, internet and online database. Dragiewicz et al. (2019) also discussed the most prevalent technology-facilitated abuses between intimate partners and mentioned: repetitive texting, emailing, stalking and harassment via social media platforms, and the use of cloud-based storage and GPS data and devices as a monitoring method. All this research helps the governmental institutions to understand and regulate this type of harmful behaviour (Laxton, 2013).

The last report on domestic abuse listed on the government website lasts from 2017, and shows that for this year the costs of domestic abuse for victims was £66 billion (Rhys et al., 2019); the costs have been split up same as the framework used in 'The Economic and Social Costs of Crime' (Heeks et al., 2018) where three areas can be found: anticipation (preventive measures), consequence (property, physical and emotional harm, victims service) and response (police and criminal justice system) (Rhys et al., 2019). The amount spent is likely to be under-estimated because many victims are reluctant to report the abuse and seek support because of the shame and lack of trust that police will believe them (Fanslow and Robinson, 2010). The report does not show how costs can be distinguished between digital violence and traditional forms of domestic abuse. The report shows that stalking generates about the same percent of fear (63%) to the victims as rape (66%), being in the second place among the domestic abuse categories (Rhys et al., 2019). Looking at the results on the feeling of anxiety and panic attacks, the report shows that stalking is in the first place with 70% among the domestic abuse categories (Rhys et al., 2019). Based on the prevalence figures by type of abuse, the report shows that stalking is on the third place after violence with injury and violence without injury (Rhys et al., 2019). Groban (2016) argued that it is important to consider that offline and online stalking tend to co-occur.

The 2013 Women's Aid report on online abuse, which surveyed 307 women who had survived domestic violence, extensively examined the concept of technology-facilitated abuse in intimate relationships. The report emphasised that most stalking cases involved an online component (Laxton, 2013). The report discusses about types of abuse like online harassment and stalking, including coercive behaviour, and celebrates the new government measures which included stalking in the Protection of Freedom Act 2012 (encompassing also: following and contacting or attempting to contact a person through friends, colleagues or technology) (Laxton, 2013). In 2015, as it can be seen in the Serious Crime Act 2007, a gap in the legislation was closed by adding another offence under the article 76 'Controlling or coercive behaviour in an intimate or family relationship' (Government, 2011). In the statutory guidance framework, types of behaviour associated with coercion and control were explained, and 'monitoring a person via online communication tools or using spyware' was included (Home Office, 2015). The

Computer Misuse Act 1990 introduced the first amendments regarding the misuse of technology. This acknowledged that unauthorised access to a person's computer, with the intent to perform any activity that grants access to data or programs may result in imprisonment for no more than 12 months, or a fine (Government, 1990).

2.3 Impact of technology facilitated intimate abuse on young adults

Technology-facilitated domestic abuse is a term used to encompass a broad range of cyber-abuse or cybercrimes between partners and ex-partners (Payne, 2020). Recent studies on young adults showed that technology has a significant impact on their relationships, in a positive but also negative way facilitating abusive interactions (Mumford et al., 2022, also seen at Brown et al., 2021). The study of Brown et al. (2021) is exploring the negative impact of technology on 523 young people's relationships - aged 16-24 years old from Australia who were engaged in a relationship in the last 12 months - and is drawn on four dimensions: humiliation, sexual coercion, monitor and control, threats. Due to lack of experience in relationship and lack of knowledge on what a healthy relationship means, young people are more vulnerable to engage in technology-facilitated abuse and might have the tendency to consider it normality, even giving a romantic touch of the events (Flores and Browne, 2017; Aghtaie et al., 2018; Stonard, 2020). Young adults' unfamiliarity with the meaning of TFDA reduces their likelihood of seeking assistance if they fall victim to such conduct (Stonard et al., 2014).

The aim of Brown et al. (2021) study was to understand if multidimensional patterns of technology-facilitated abuse in relationships would be gendered, if victimisation of multidimensional patterns of technology-facilitated abuse in relationships would differ by gender compared with victimisation on individual technology-facilitated abuse dimensions. They also wanted to understand if women victims of technology-facilitated abuse in relationships would report greater fear and distress than men victims. The findings show the importance of examining the behavioural patterns, and the possible inaccuracies of measuring behavioural frequencies alone (Brown et al., 2021). Many debates between scholars showed that there is no unique view regarding how technology-facilitated domestic abuse can be gendered, and Anderson (1995) discussed that socialisation into masculinity can be theorised to explain why women are less violent than men. Conversely, Benjamin (2013) explains from a psychoanalytical view that socialisation itself does not cause men's violence, but the vulnerability and instability of men's identity makes men become violent to recover their sense of self. Anderson (1995) highlights the significance of considering that offending behaviour can have distinct outcomes for men and women. Similarly, examining victimisation through a gender lens reveals variations in the impact of the same

situation. Brown et al. (2021) argued that gendered patterns of behaviour would be exemplified by the differing, yet significant, effects experienced by young men and women as a result of various multi-dimensional technology-facilitated abuses in the relationships. This can help government and organisations who offer help for victims give more specialised support, but also help scholars and policy-makers understand this emerging and detrimental form of abuse (Brown et al., 2021).

In Brown et al. (2021) study it can be seen that young male and female adults have experienced similar psychological impact when they were victims of technology facilitated abuse, showing fear and distress on different multi-dimensional TFA experiences, but on humiliation males expressed more emotional and psychological affect than females, and on sexual coercion female show more emotional and psychological distress than male (as seen also on Zweig et al., 2013). In other studies was argued that overall women experience more emotional and psychological distress when exposed to technology-facilitated domestic abuse (Barter et al., 2009; Bennett et al., 2011). As Harris and Woodlock (2019) argue, many studies were conducted on young people and centres on electronic dating violence (Borrajó et al., 2015; Wolford-Clevenger et al., 2016; Agthaie et al., 2018; Lara, 2020) because they are the generation for whom the virtual environment and the use of technology represent a large share in their life. While technology may have benefits for people's daily lives, it can also have a negative impact on their relationships. It is imperative to understand this impact to assist governments in devising ways to prevent and ensure safety (Stonard, 2020; Caridade et al., 2019).

2.4 TFDA, between normalisation and regulation

The twenty-first century can be considered the beginning of the research into TFDA and domestic violence. In the past approximately twenty years, the frequency and nature of abusive behaviours reported by the women which were participants in the research already done, suggest that TFDA is a key form of abuse needing closer attention (Douglas et al., 2019). Harris and Woodlock (2019) wrote one of the articles that analyses and draws attention towards Digital Coercive Control (DCC), here they reviewed studies. First from Woodlock (2013), called the Smartsafe study, made in Australia where he reviewed technology facilitated Digital Violence (DV) from victims and support practitioners' perspective using a mixed method approach (included focus groups with DV sector professionals and two online surveys with 152 DV support practitioners and 46 victims). Second from George and Harris (2014), named Landscapes study where in-depth interviews were conducted in rural spaces with female victims who survived from family violence (with 30 females victims, 19 lawyers, 3 magistrates and 24 DV workers), where grounded theory methodology was used to analyse data. Compared with the previous study discussed in this paper, in Harris and Woodlock (2019) article was emphasised the idea

of gender blind literature, which limits the full understanding of digital coercive control. Coercive control in his nature is a gendered theory where men try to enhance their status by exploiting women's inequalities (Stark, 2007), the same argument being used by Hester (2010). Poland (2016) argued that the online environment is a land ruled by men, where cyber-sexism needs to stop because it affects women's lives, opinions and experiences when online. There is also research which shows that women spend more time than men texting, video chatting, creating and maintaining relationship through online platforms (Kimbrough et al., 2013). On the opposite side, the researchers showed that males spend more time online (Morahan-Martin, 1998), using more computers and technology than women (He and Freeman, 2010). Scholars also argued that computer and internet was created by men for men (Weiser, 2000; Gilbert et al., 2003), and women do not feel so comfortable with computers, compared to men do, and can feel anxious about the use of technology (Harrison et al., 1997).

The findings from the Smartsafe study arose the idea of 'spacelessness' (seen in Stark, 2007; and in detail discussed in Fitz-Gibbon et al., 2018), in which the victims do not feel safe anywhere because they feel monitored and controlled. The study was also showing that authorities recommend that victims should go offline or stop using the technology and smart equipment in their possession as a safety and precaution method (Woodlock, 2013). The survey also showed that, from 56% of the victims who did not seek help, 85% mentioned that they were embarrassed (Woodlock, 2013). Another aspect revealed by the study is that victims consider online stalking as normality, and perpetrators' repeated contact attempts may be perceived as "romantic" behaviour. (Woodlock, 2013; also discussed by Flores and Browne, 2017; Aghtaie et al., 2018; Stonard, 2020; Brown et al., 2021).

In the Landscapes research, aspects of how women in non-urban area are experiencing and responding to digital violence were highlighted (George and Harris, 2014). All respondents experienced abuse through technology and most of them experienced stalking via technology (George and Harris, 2014). In rural spaces, home is not a safe place for the victims, and there is a direct association between gender constructs, the oppression of women, and the normalisation of violence towards women. (George and Harris, 2014; idea discussed also by Weller et al., 2013). The rise in women's geographical isolation reflects a discovery from a 1992 investigation in which the victims stated that their screams were unheard by anyone. (George and Harris, 2014; National Committee on Violence Against Women, 1992). Another problem was raised by the victims, saying that the feeling of unsafe comes also from the fact that everybody knows everybody's business and is hard to go to the authorities (George and Harris, 2014). The self-blame in both analysed studies was considered a significant barrier to help-seeking (Harris and Woodlock, 2019). In Landscapes study, it could also be seen that one of the prevention

strategies applied by the authorities was to ask victims to stop using technology and close their online accounts (George and Harris, 2014).

From both studies, the idea of normalisation arose, and many studies show that between 22% and 93% of participants (males and females) have experienced different forms of digital aggression (see Melander, 2010; Burke et al., 2011; Bennett et al., 2011; Borrajo et al., 2015; Ybarra et al., 2017), which can complement the idea that such behaviour is somewhat tolerated or standardised (Harris and Woodlock, 2019). Among youth, the idea of normalisation is stronger recognised because of their experiences of power and control through technology, which takes an important part of their daily life (see Lucero et al., 2014; Temple et al.; 2016). Some forms of technology-facilitated domestic abuse and stalking have the risk of being considered a normal behaviour by the victims because of the few contexts that can further be discussed (Harris and Woodlock, 2019). One of them is the lifetime experiences that victims might have as children or adults that make them expect to be surrounded by violence (George and Harris, 2014). Second context might be for the minorities or people who lived in societies where law did not yet regulate this kind of behaviour, and groups which have been exposed to systemic discrimination might normalise the aggressive behaviour (Immigrant women's domestic violence service, 2006; Jordan and Philips, 2013). The third idea suggests that technology-facilitated domestic abuse may be seen as a romantic gesture rather than abusive conduct, due to the frequent use of technology by partners, creating a thin line between keeping close contact and controlling or stalking (see Melander 2010; Burke et al., 2011; Bennett et al., 2011; Woodlock, 2013; Borrajo et al., 2015; Ybarra et al., 2017). There is still a great need for further understanding of how digital coercive control is similar and at the same time different from the classic in-person abuse and stalking, and how all intersect with technology (Harris and Woodlock, 2019).

Havard and Lefevre (2020) done a study which was conducted on twelve women who identified mobile phones as an important factor in the abuse they experienced from their partners, and was conducted through the qualitative approach using individual interviews. The study took into consideration any ways in which mobile phones featured within the victims' domestic abuse. The data were thematically categorised according with Duluth Domestic Abuse Intervention Program (DDAIP) Power and Control wheel - intimidation, emotional abuse, isolation, denial, minimisation and blame, using children, using male privilege, economic abuse, coercion and threats (Pence, 2002). The research showed that intimidation with the use of the phone is the most common tactic of coercive control. According to the emotional and psychological abuse theme, with the help of mobile phones perpetrators' behaviour was designed to intimidate, frighten, undermine and distress women and most of the data from the

research could be additionally classified under this theme (Havard and Lefevre, 2020). The phone was also used to isolate women from family and friends. As an example of intimidation, according to a respondent, her partner inflicted harm upon himself in order to take pictures threatening to show it to the police as evidence that she was aggressive (Havard and Lefevre, 2020). Stark (2007) also discussed the tactic of intimidation and control and considered that such micro-regulation is used to control women's everyday lives, making coercion appear normal. The study shows also that where children are involved, some perpetrators used the mobile phones to extend their power and control over the kids (Havard and Lefevre, 2020; Douglas et al., 2019). Havard and Lefevre's (2020) study showed that there was no exception when talked about their partners' control over their phones. It looks like men check women's phone and some perpetrators behave like the women's phone belongs to them. Coercion and threats enacted through phones were present in some women's lives by men manipulating the women to agree in checking each other's phones but in the end they were the only one allowed to check women's phone, sending threatening messages and creating the feeling that nowhere is safe, being another method highlighted in the research (Havard and Lefevre, 2020; Douglas et al., 2019).

Beyond the Power and control wheel, in the research were revealed other techniques used with the mobile phones help, techniques that mediate coercive control and abuse: tracking women's locations through GPS, control scrutiny of various forms of physical or virtual contact with others, and virtual spying at a distance through audio or video links (Havard and Lefevre, 2020). These techniques served for multiple inter-related purposes like intimidate and threaten, coerce and manipulate, harm emotionally and psychologically, assert privilege and ownership of all aspects of the women's life, approach underlined in many studies in the past decade (Harris and Woodlock, 2019; Douglas et al., 2019; Havard and Lefevre, 2020; Brown et al., 2021). With this research, Havard and Lefevre (2020) managed to point out the importance of multiple possibilities of phone surveillance and how this affects victims. Their work had an important contribution towards a revised wheel which was approved by DDAIP and because the Wheel is used across many countries and this should grow awareness and lay out clearer guidance for practice use (Havard and Lefevre, 2020).

In summary, therefore, the prior arguments have drawn attention to the weaknesses of existing literature regarding how knowledgeable women are on technology-facilitated domestic abuse methods and regulations, and their perception on this subject, and the subsequent need for further research. In synthesising these prior points of, and in guiding the remainder of the research, the following research questions have been generated:

- 1) What role does communication technology have in the lives (intimate relationships) of 30-45 year old London females?
- 2) How knowledgeable are 30–45-year-old females in London regarding the law and technology-facilitated domestic violence methods?
- 3) In view of the relationship between domestic violence and digital technologies, what policy reforms can be made to better protect women?

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Introduction

The purpose of this chapter is to describe the research approach and methods employed in this study, which is informed by a left-realist framework. This will offer a better understanding of technology-facilitated domestic abuse from a victim's perspective, relying on the well-known aspects of 'square of crime' - state, public, victim and offender (Cullen and Wilcox, 2010). The researcher will not focus on offender's behaviour but on the tools that technology offer to facilitate domestic abuse. The research is aiming to understand the experiences and needs of those who are at risk of being victimised, but also aims to identify and propose new policies and interventions that address the root causes of technology-facilitated domestic abuse. A left realist approach will help the researcher emphasise the importance of involving communities, private and public sector to address the subject (Cullen and Wilcox, 2010). The researcher will further describe the research design and methods used in this study, which were designed to align with the principles of left realism and facilitate an in-depth exploration of the experiences and perspectives of adult women in London.

3.2 Design and Methods

The method used for this primary research is qualitative, and individual semi-structured interviews were conducted to gather and analyse data. There is a significant difference between the quantitative method, which explains the causes of changes with the help of numbers that allow the study of occurrence phenomena (Firestone, 1987), and, alternatively, a qualitative method which is exploring the meaning of events or behaviours as they are understood by the participants with the use of interviews, focus groups, case studies or observational methods (Neuman, 2013). As Anderson (1995) wrote, compared with the quantitative method, the qualitative method offers the possibility to gather in depth rich data which does not limit the participants to give 'yes' or 'no' answers, helping increase the richness of social research.

In any methodological approach, epistemology is central (King et al., 2018) and, together with the idea of integrity, reveals the importance of the connection between strategy, design, questions, methods and nature of the research (Marshall and Rossman, 2006). Social constructivist paradigm, which describes the world as a unique reality created in the process of social exchange (Schwandt, 1994), has been used in the present research. In qualitative research, the researcher believes that the participants' sociological experiences and understanding of their own beliefs, behaviours and reasons can generate

knowledge (Arghode, 2012). As well, subjectivity is a specific ontological aspect of qualitative research, a fact that makes researchers consider that findings are not generalisable, being specifically shaped by the participants' experiences (Arghode, 2012).

An important part of the research process is framing the questions, and a novice researcher can make common mistakes, like seeking to establish general trends or causal relationships (King et al., 2018). The study is not taking into consideration to be gendered, but, considering the size of the paper and the time limitation, the researcher needed to narrow down the researched area and participants. To narrow the spectrum, the present paper framed the research questions and interviewed only London women from the age range of 30 - 45 years old focusing on how knowledgeable they are regarding the law and technology-facilitated domestic abuse. A broader scope can be a limitation for understanding the people's life in the researched context, and can be difficult to draw a reliable and valid conclusion (King et al., 2018). For interviewing, the present research used semi-structured question which helped participants explore and tell their experiences in a non-restrictive manner, but also helped the researcher not lose the focus and not shift the answers outside of the scope, helping engage in dialog exchange (Husband, 2020). The researcher did not use the focus group method because this method generates information from collective views, and the researcher needs to understand individual opinions and experiences (Gill et al., 2008).

In a qualitative research, it is important to decide what the most appropriate sampling method is for the researched subject (Alvi, 2016). The present study used the snowball sampling method, a non-probability sampling technique (Alvi, 2016), which consists of identifying the first participants who fit the criteria and ask them to recommend other possible participants from their circle of friends, family or colleagues (Tracy, 2019). Some of the advantages of this method is that is cost effective and not time consuming, but as a drawback can have the limitation of sampling biases due to network connections (Alvi, 2016). For a better understanding, and with the scope of gaining more knowledge about the researched subject, grounded theory it would have been ideal to use, but the size of the paper and the time frame do not permit the researcher to choose the mentioned theory. The researcher analysed the data through a thematic analysis, which uses a systematic model that analyses the data line by line, creating codes which are linked and categorised by themes becoming the foundation for constructs and relationships (Urquhart, 2012). To gain thematic insight into data, NVivo Software was used, this system is used in qualitative research to generate codes and themes. During the construction of thematic analysis and critical discussion chapters, the researcher used a diary to write all the ideas generated by the analytical process.

3.3 Ethics

The Researcher follows the ethical conduct of criminological research as acknowledged from the British Society of Criminology website, which provides guidelines for a good practice and high ethical standards (British Society of Criminology, 2015). The research is focused on the safeguarding and protection of the interviewee. Because the study targets potential victims of cybercrime, there can be a negative psychological impact by having them relive the events. The researcher created an informed consent that goes through the details of the study and possible sensitive experiences to help respondents to decide if they want to participate or not. The possibility of withdrawing their participation at any time was offered to all the respondents; all the gathered data are anonym and treated as confidential information, being password protected by the researcher on private property computer. The issue of trust may be raised because a relationship based on trust cannot be created from the beginning, but the responsibility of confidentiality in social research can lay a foundation of trust in which the participants will feel that their information will be safe and not used beyond the purpose of the research (Finch, 2001). For the purpose of anonymity in this paper real names were not used, this measure being a part of the confidentiality and protection section, 'the conventional practice is to ensure the participants' that names and identifying details are expunged from public records of the research and that high levels of confidentiality of data are maintained during the research process (Macleod et al., 2018, p. 227).

Informed consent plays an important role in the interviewing process and provides information about the focus of the research and what the participants are consenting to (Silverman and Marvasti, 2008). As a result, each participant received a printed consent form to read and sign (Appendix A) prior to the interview. The interview took place face to face in a public place and data were gathered in writing by the researcher. The reason for not recording the sessions was because some of the participants did not agree to record the interview. Before the start of the interview, the researcher made sure that the participants had all questions answered and that the purpose of the interview and the content of the consent form were clearly understood. Each interview took approximately thirty minutes and at the end, each participant was reminded about the details and the possibility of withdrawing the consent. The questions from the interview can be seen in the Appendix B, but full interview transcripts were not included because the participants did not consent to the publication of their complete interviews. They were concerned that their identities could be revealed based on the stories they shared. The transcripts of the interview were kept on the researcher's computer, which is password protected and no access has been granted to third persons.

Chapter 4: Thematic Analysis

4.1 Introduction

For this research, seven interviews were conducted and provided an in-depth understanding of how knowledgeable 30 to 45 years old women in London about law and technology-facilitated domestic abuse are, and how communication technology affects their relationship with their partners or ex partners. For a better understanding of London women's experiences and perception over the impact of communication technology on their intimate relationship, further research needs to be done with a larger sample. The researcher used thematic analysis and identified four key themes (Appendix C), which incorporate significant findings: Female experiences of TFDA, Female perception of communication technology, Awareness problem, Formal and informal safety measures.

4.2 Female experiences of TFDA

In their answers, five of the participants disclosed information about their experiences in abusive relationships and how technology affected them emotionally and socially. The other two participants explained that they did not have abusive experiences in their relationships, but it can also be taken into account that they might not be aware of any abusive behaviour through technology that might happen in the past or present – information gathered under the code 'Harmful behaviour'. The five participants who discussed how their partners and ex-partners used communication through technology to coerce them and stalk them, explaining that they tried to cut their connections with friends or cut access to their bank accounts. The participants argued that was a difficult period where they felt that their freedom was taken away, and worried about their partners' reaction when did not answer to their calls or did not let them check their phones.

'I was not feeling safe to silent my phone for a few hours in order to be able to focus on my work because I was afraid of his reactions if I did not answer. I was feeling that my freedom was taken away.' (Participant 2)

'My ex-partner had a routine in asking me to constantly share my location, he was calling me with video to see where and with whom I was.' (Participant 3)

Deprivation of freedom was also confirmed by five participants' answers regarding their opinion on closing their accounts to protect themselves from their partner or ex-partner behaviour.

'No, to close all your accounts is not a good solution because there is all your life in it.' (Participant 4)

Asked about what makes them feel more afraid of online or offline methods of abuse, four of them answered that the offline abuse is something that they consider more harmful and give them more reasons to be scared because they might not escape when it happens. Among these participants, two of them were the ones that said they did not have incidents involving technology which might affect their perception. Another four respondents argued that the online abuse is more psychologically damaging and can also affect their image on a longer term, all of them being victims of this type of abuse in the past. There were also considerations from some respondents that offline domestic abuse can put you in real danger, and others argued that the online domestic abuse is easier to ignore when is too much. But some participants also discussed how both methods can create distress.

'Both methods are damaging, on short term I am more afraid of the classic domestic abuse but on longer term the online abuse can be more damaging for the image and psychologically.' (Participant 2)

Overall, from respondents' perception, it can be argued that offline domestic abuse it causes more fear because it can harm people physically and emotionally, but online domestic abuse can affect reputation and psychological state more on longer term, even though some respondents might try to ignore and try to find different protection measures as it can be seen further in thematic analysis.

4.3 Female perception of communication technology

Under the umbrella of this theme, the researcher gathered evidence divided in two codes. First code analysed is 'the impact of communication technology' on London women aged 30-45 years old intimate relationship, and it was found that most of the women considered that technology and internet helps them to have a faster and better communication, but five of them argued that there is a fine line between healthier communication and controlling, and when the boundaries are crossed, then abusive behaviour emerge.

'It is a good thing because you can get in contact very easy and more often, but when the boundaries are overstepped, and it starts to be very often and without any real reason, than it can be harmful and abusive.' (Participant 2)

'I do believe that communication through technology can have a negative impact on the relationship when is used excessively and when the intention is to manipulate the other person.' (Participant 5)

To understand how women in London perceive TFDA, the respondents were also asked about their willingness to know more about this kind of abuse, and the second code named 'The impact of awareness about type of TFDA and protection measures' revealed that all the respondents considered awareness a way to help them prevent and protect themselves and the children from these abusive actions, and another one of the total number also argued that it might help her to:

'...trust more the authorities after this.' (Participant 3).

4.4 Awareness problem

The awareness problem theme incorporates information regarding how knowledgeable the participants are about the law on technology-facilitated domestic abuse and what type of abuses they know. When asked about their knowledge on the law that can protect them from digital abuse four of the respondents said that they have no knowledge and the other three explained that they know it exists, but they do not know any details about how the law regulates this type of behaviour. All the participants also showed a willingness to know and understand the law on TFDA. These answers are important because without knowing the law, it is difficult for the victims to know and understand their rights and how authorities can intervene to protect them.

'I know that it exists, but I don't know exactly how much it protects you and which one are the laws that take in consideration online offences.' (Participant 1)

The awareness of the technology-facilitated abuse methods was another point discussed in the interview, and all the participants showed some knowledge about the technological tools that someone in their proximity might use to harm them. Even all together, they mentioned most of the technology-facilitated abuse types, the participants separately showed in their answers that some of them know more than the others about these methods and tools.

'I know about gps tag and tracking software on phones, tracking and stalking through social media, breaking into my e-mail address, laptops or phones or other accounts, blackmail through messages and intimate pictures, stalking through messages and phone calls.' (Participant 2)

'In my case, he used the online access to my bank account in order to transfer all my money into an account that I was not having access to. Access to my personal accounts, phone, social media.' (Participant 4)

'It can limit your access to online environment and can take away your phone and other devices. The accounts can be accessed without consent. Stalking through social media and gps localisation, shaming or blackmail by disclosing intimate pictures and information.' (Participant 5)

'Slander, shaming. Gps location to find you.' (Participant 7)

The awareness of the methods of technology-facilitated abuse can be linked with the theme regarding Female experiences of TFDA, because as it can be seen in the participants answers coded as harmful behaviour, that the respondents who mentioned their harmful experiences have the tendency to be aware of more technology facilitated abuse types, being also strongly related with these experiences; compared with the respondents who said they did not experience negative behaviour on the matter and have less knowledge.

4.5 Formal and informal safety measures

When asked about their opinion if police should be informed about TFDA when it happens, most of the respondents considered that the police needs to be informed about this type of behaviour, and one of the respondents argued that this should be reported only in some cases:

'...only if they would hardly degenerate to make me feel afraid for my safety'
(Participant 2)

Even they had a positive response on this question, they also argued that they do not feel totally protected by the authorities, some of them not knowing what to expect from them - this might be one of the effects of not knowing the law on TFDA. There were also to extremely opposite answers from two of the respondents where trust was either given in full or not at all.

'Not totally protected, I do think that police are somehow limited, but I do think that once the situation is taken to court, you get fully protected.' (Participant 1)

'I do not know what to expect if I go to the police because I never tried. I saw my neighbours interacting with the police for domestic violence, but what I could see from those experiences is that the police have a mediator role more than protector.' (Participant 2)

Out of the five women who experienced TFDA, three of them went to the police as a protection measure. Among the measures that the respondents could use or think about it were mentioned also changing the passwords to all the accounts, closing some of the accounts or changing phone numbers, set up healthy boundaries, and asking for help to IT professionals or to domestic violence associations.

The researcher also asked about their opinion on the idea to go completely offline, giving up to their social media accounts and changing mobile phones to escape from the abuser. Five of the participants considered that is not a suitable solution and that they would feel like their freedom is taken away. Two of these five also argued:

'...he will try to find other ways' (Participant 5)

Two of the participants who said that is a good idea also mentioned that they would open new accounts in a short time. The feeling of being deprived of freedom was visible also in the first theme, which collected data on the psychological and sociological harm caused by technology-facilitated domestic abuse. Women perceive that this form of abuse has a significant impact on their daily lives. These two situations in which respondents were having the feeling that their freedom is taken away are complementing each other and can be both perceived as abuses. First, the perpetrator can use technology against the victim using their own private phones, accounts or other devices, and second, they might need to stop using all these devices and platforms as a protection measure, which they consider it extreme and not helpful.

Chapter 5: Critical Discussion

First question in the present study was to understand what role communication technology in 30 to 45 years old London women have in their intimate relationship. The study was conducted taking into consideration only adult women's opinion, but the subject can be expanded on the entire population because communication through technology has an impact on every person's life, 'is attached to or implanted in the human body' as Katz (2003) argued in his book about personal communication technologies. The present paper confirms the idea that women victimisation is more prevalent in the context of TFDA (Lenhart et al., 2016; Ybarra et al., 2017; Dunn, 2020). Information, about the participants experiences with their partners or ex-partners when communication through technology was involved, were gathered under the code 'Harmful behaviour' and found that five out of seven women have been in situations where they became victims of technology-facilitated domestic abuses like coercion, controlling and stalking. As well, two out of five mentioned that they also used, at list once, their partners' mobile phones to control their contacts and messages, arguing that this did not become a habit. At the same time, the researcher observed - from the respondents' answers, also seen in Brown et al. (2021) - that communication through technology is omnipresent in couples' life. A different perspective is offered by Brown et al. (2021) in their study about technology-facilitated abuse in relationship and the impact on young people, showing that both male and females experienced same frequency of monitoring, control and threats through technology, but the impact on gender was different. After analysing the respondents' answers, and as it can be seen in the specific literature, a conclusion can be drawn, meaning that unless is about digital dating abuse (e.g. Borrajo et al., 2015; Brown and Hegarty, 2018; Ybarra et al., 2017), there are not so many studies on technology-facilitated domestic abuse (Woodlock, 2017). All evidence presented above shows that further research on adult males and females should be conducted for a better understanding of how communication technology is used in an abusive manner. The findings will help police to better protect and prevent future abusive behaviour facilitated through technology. Additionally, considering the constant technological development that creates new opportunities for abusive behaviour, the government could enhance its legislation.

According to the findings of this research, participants revealed that online abuse can cause long term psychological harm, and the need to go offline to safeguard themselves leads to feelings of freedom deprivation, answers coded in 'Protection measures' under theme 'Formal and informal safety measures'. These findings come to confirm Woodlock (2013) observations from Smartsafe study were

police advised women to go offline, and the respondents claimed the same discomfort (also seen at George and Harris, 2014). Poland's (2016) argument that the online environment is ruled by men and cyber-sexism affects women's online experiences is consistent with the findings of this research. The present research would benefit from a criminological perspective that considers oppression and discrimination as crucial factors in understanding crime. As Young (1989) argues, Left Realist theory offers such an approach, which emphasises social justice, inequality, and power in a broader overview of criminal behaviour. This framework can help better understand technology-facilitated domestic abuse as a criminological issue that requires society and authorities to take an active role in prevention, awareness, and safety solutions. The present research can serve as a starting point for future research about how males and females use and behave in a world where technology is omnipresent and is continuously developing and offering new possibilities. This will help public and private sector understand if the fight against technology facilitated-domestic abuse can be won with the help of the same general tool 'technology', and can work together to develop software that can be incorporated in mobile devices like phones, tablets and laptops. Technological devices offer the possibility of gathering data about possible or imminent threats, and automatically alerting the authorities. This technology has the potential to provide timely and accurate information, enabling authorities to take proactive measures and prevent Technology-Facilitated Domestic Abuse (TFDA) from occurring.

Most of the interviewed women consider that classic domestic abuse generates short term psychological and physiological distress, making them feel afraid for their life and safety. They also argued that the psychological negative impact that online abuse has it generates a longer-term effect - was analysed in the previous chapter under the theme 'Female experiences of TFDA'. Most of the participants in the study explained that communication through technology has its benefits and help partners organise their life better especially when kids are involved, but they also argued that there is a line than it is easy to cross, and, from their own experiences showed in the previous chapter code 'impact of communication technology', this type of communication started to have a negative impact on their lives. There can also be identified an international shift from well-known physical violence and domestic abuse to a new pattern of coercive control mediated by mobile phones (Havard and Lefevre, 2020), and most of the existing research shows that there are similar or worse negative emotional and psychological consequences of coercive control compared to physical abuse (Crossman et al., 2016; Havard and Lefevre, 2020). This is an aspect that needs to be taken into consideration by the authorities and scientists, and further research can help to overcome this long-term effect of TFDA by finding additional safety measures with public and private sector's help.

Throughout the present research, it was revealed that there is a lack of awareness when it comes to the existing law about TFDA, as shown by the code 'Knowledge of law' under theme 'Awareness problem'. All the participants mentioned that they are not knowledgeable about how law can protect them from this type of abuse, as well as disclosing that they are not totally aware of all the tools and methods that can be used against them with the help of internet and technological devices. Tanczer et al. (2018) argued that there is a lack of awareness and technical capacity to respond to technology-facilitated abuse both in statutory and voluntary support services, explaining that there is an urgent requirement for further training of the police force and allocation of resources towards the identification and comprehension of the negative effects of technology-facilitated abuse. This includes understanding the relevant laws pertaining to technology-facilitated abuse and knowing how to react to reports of such incidents while providing a safe and encouraging space for the diverse group of victims/survivors affected by technology-facilitated abuse (Flynn et al., 2023).

Awareness is strongly related to the respondents' reluctance to trust that police can help victims in this kind of situations, which was one of the concerns showed by the respondents of this study who argued also that the police have a more intermediary role than a protective one in these types of situations. Young (1999) also explained that, from a left realist perspective, some people who experienced systemic oppression or have witnessed abuses of power by authorities may be afraid of abuse. Other studies also showed that women are afraid and ashamed to go to the police because nobody believes them (Woodlock, 2013; Fanslow and Robinson, 2010). This fear is not unfounded, as some policies and practices implemented in the name of left realism have been criticised for disproportionately affecting marginalised communities and perpetuating systemic inequality (Young, 1999). At the same time, most of the respondents of this study consider that police should be informed when this kind of behaviour takes place – being one of the measures that they consider it normal to apply- idea discussed also in other studies (Flynn et al., 2023; Woodlock 2013; Woodlock et al., 2019; Lexton, 2013). As shown in the previous chapter, it can be observed that awareness of legislation and of the digital methods used by the perpetrators is an important issue which needs to be addressed by the state authorities together with the private sector and communities. The researcher proposes that authorities create awareness programs aimed at educating young and adult public about the importance of the Technology-Facilitated Abuse law and methods of protection. These programs should be developed in collaboration with charities, educational institutions, and platforms/software developers to reach a wider audience. By doing so, authorities can increase public awareness about the serious implications of TFDA and

promote a culture of zero tolerance towards it. These awareness programs should be regularly evaluated to ensure their effectiveness and to identify any areas that may need improvement. The involvement of charities and social media platforms is essential for reaching vulnerable groups, such as victims of technology-facilitated domestic abuse, and providing them with the necessary support and resources. Overall, this proposal aims to create a safer environment for all individuals and to prevent TFDA from happening in the first place.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

The literature presented in this paper illustrates that technology-facilitated domestic abuse became a major issue around the world in the past decades, young people and adult women being more exposed to this type of abusive behaviour (Brown et al., 2021; Woodlock, 2013). Most of the studies discuss the emotional and psychological impact on the victims, as well as the prevalence and different methods used by perpetrators (Tjaden and Thoennes, 2000; Lara, 2020; Brown et al., 2021). In the research qualitative method was used and seven semi-structured interviews were conducted. Four themes were identified, which are related to adult London women's view regarding the impact of communication technology in their intimate relationships, their experiences regarding technology-facilitated abuse, the awareness problem, and the formal/informal safety measures. The thematic analysis revealed that most of the respondents have experienced at least one form of abuse through technology in their relationship with partners or ex-partners, considering that there is a thin line between a positive and negative impact of communication through technology in their lives. Another important finding was that women are not aware of how existing law can protect them and showed interest in understanding more about the law and ways in how they prevent and identify potential threats facilitated by technology.

As showed in this primary research, and previously argued by various researchers, technology-facilitated domestic abuse overcomes spatiality, generating constant emotional and psychological distress, the perpetrators becoming omnipresent in the victims' lives, behaving in a coercive and controlling manner (Woodlock, 2013; George and Harris, 2014). Based on the evidence shown in the present study, there is a need for policy reform that helps in creating awareness on the law that protects and helps victims of technology-facilitated domestic abuse, and not at last the individuals and police need to be trained according with the new technological tools that offenders can use to engage in abusive behaviours. For a better understanding and generalisation of the findings, further research should be conducted, which will help public and private sector find the right methods to educate and inform the public regarding law and methods of technology-facilitated abuse.

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Appendix A

CONSENT FORM

Participant Briefing

Thank you for considering taking part in this study. I inform you below about the nature and purpose of the study, and I will answer to your questions to the best of my abilities. I read, understood and I agree to abide the British Society of Criminology Code of Conduct, Ethical Principals and Guidelines for conducting research with human participants.

In the present study it will be explored how communication through technology impacts the relationship between partners or ex-partners through the perspective of adult London women participants aged 30-45 years old, and if they are knowledgeable of the law and technology-facilitated domestic abuse. The results of the study will be used for the dissertation paper of the BSc Criminology and Psychology degree and will be included in the research report.

The interview will take approximately 30-40 minutes and the answers will be anonymous and could not be linked to identify the participants. All collected data will be stored on a secure password protected device and will be accessible only to the researcher and supervisor, however extracts of the data will be presented in a research document which may possibly be published online. The participants are free to choose whether to participate, participation being entirely voluntary. Also, the participant can request to withdraw their consent for participation at any time during the study, in this situation all the answers will be destroyed. When the respondents will decide to participate, then they will be required to sign a consent form.

The study does not have any predicted disadvantages or risk-taking components. However, the participants might find that some specific questions are emotional. If the participant was a victim of technology-facilitated domestic abuse, might find some difficulties in answering to questions that trigger specific psychologically harmful memories, which might need to be considered before taking the decision to participate to the study. Taking part of this study requires to be 18 years old or over.

The participants' withdrawal needs to be informed not later than 15th of April 2023, the request will be sent via e-mail to the following address: [REDACTED]

Participant statement

I have been invited to participate in research about the impact that communication through technology has on London women relationship with their partners or ex-partners, and the awareness of the law and technology facilitated domestic abuse. I have read the foregoing information, and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have been asked and have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Name of the participant.....

Signature of the participant.....

Date.....

Appendix B

Questions used to interview the participants

1. How can you describe the use of technology in your relationship with your partner or Ex partner?
2. Do you consider that police need to be informed about certain behaviours regarding technology facilitated abuse when happen?
3. What do you do to protect yourself online?
4. What do you know about the law on technology facilitated domestic violence?
5. Do you consider yourself protected by the law enforcement organisations when online?
6. What kind of technology-facilitated domestic abuse are you aware of?
7. Do you consider a good solution to close all your online accounts including changing your mobile phone in order to escape from online stalking or abusive online behaviour from partner/ex-partner?
8. What makes you more afraid of: the online or the offline domestic abuse?
9. Would you consider helpful to be formally informed about the ways someone in your proximity can abuse you through technology and online activity, and learn ways to protect yourself?

Appendix C

Themes and codes generated in NVivo

<input type="radio"/> Awareness problem	0	0
<input type="radio"/> Abuse awareness	7	8
<input type="radio"/> Knowledge of law	7	7
<input type="radio"/> Will to learn	7	8
<input type="radio"/> Female experineces of TFDA	0	0
<input type="radio"/> Fear of abuse	7	7
<input type="radio"/> Freedom depravation	6	8
<input type="radio"/> Harmful behaviour	7	13
<input type="radio"/> Female perception of communication technology	0	0
<input type="radio"/> Impact of awareness about type of TFA and protection measures	4	4
<input type="radio"/> Impact of communication technology	7	8
<input type="radio"/> Formal and Informal Safety measures	0	0
<input type="radio"/> Authorities protection	7	8
<input type="radio"/> Intention to report	7	7
<input type="radio"/> Protection measures	7	22